

Magnetic fields and line profiles variability in spectra of OBA stars

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**1947 - the stellar magnetic field is firstly discovered
(78 Vir, ApEuCrSr, Babcock, 1947)**

More than 1000 magnetic MS stars are known now

Only ~ 5-7% OBA stars are magnetic

	MiMeS	BOB
Number stars surveyed	~525	138
Number fields detected	~35	14
Detection rate	7±1%	~5-6%
Magnetic field fraction at ZAMS?		

Magnetic flux distribution for massive OB stars, **WR stars**, pulsars and magnetars: $F = 4\pi \langle B \rangle R^2$

Magnetic field distributions (Medvedev et al. 2017, AN, 338, 910-918)

Magnetic field distribution for AB, OB, and O stars (model without magnetic field dissipation). Gray histograms are the magnetic field measurements. Black lines and dotted lines show the mean model distribution and deviations from the mean. The gray filled area corresponds to the 95% confidence level.

Parameters of optimal population synthesis models both without (M_0) and with (M_1) magnetic field dissipation

Stars	Model	$\langle \log \Phi \rangle$	σ
BA	M_0	26.42 ± 0.04	0.50 ± 0.05
	M_1	26.83 ± 0.07	0.33 ± 0.07
OB	M_0	26.51 ± 0.11	0.33 ± 0.07
	M_1	26.90 ± 0.17	0.53 ± 0.09
O	M_0	26.95 ± 0.35	0.53 ± 0.35
	M_1	27.29 ± 0.47	0.51 ± 0.07
OBA	M_0	26.45 ± 0.05	0.50 ± 0.05
	M_1	26.87 ± 0.07	0.35 ± 0.06

Fast line profile variability in spectra of OBA stars on minute and second scales

Variability of the line profiles is an indicator of the presence of the magnetic field

The characteristic time of variability :
Irregular variability – 0.1- 5 minutes
Regular variability?

Observation requirements :

Typical time of a variability ~ plasma cooling time ~ plasma recombination time ~ 6 seconds - 5 minutes

A typical amplitude of variability ~ 10^{-2} : 10^{-3} of the continuum flux

$\Delta T < 5 \text{ min (5 - 300 s) S/N } \sim 2000$

Program stars for searching the ultra-fast line profile variations (~ 2500 spectra)

SAO – BTA (6m telescope) with SCORPIO spectrograph. $R \sim 2000$ $S/N \geq 2000$

Star	Sp.Class	V	N_{sp}	Exp (s)	Date
HD 93521	O9Vp	7.06	529	3	19/20.01.2015
rho Leo	B1Iab	3.87	1271	1	19/20.01.2015 + 20/21.01.2015
alf02 CVn	A0spe	2.90	387	1	21/22.01.2015
HD 21389	A0Ia	4.54	330	11	25/26.09.2016

HD 93521

HD 93521

O9.5III

V=7.03

**Non-radially
pulsating
variable star**

HD 93521 H_β line profile variations

$$\Delta I = \pm 2\%$$

H_{δ} + HeII 4686: dynamical spectra

Fourier spectra: H β

Dirty Spectrum

Clean Spectrum

Parameters of the line profile variability in spectra of program stars

Object	Sp. type	Typical time of a variability	A kind of the variability
HD 93521	O9.5III	4 – 25 min	Regular
ρ Leo	B1Iab	1 – 90 min	Regular + Irregular
α^2 CVn	A0VpSiEu	18 – 135 min	Regular

High-frequency components of line profile variations: ρ Leo

H_{δ}

$v_1 = 0.2 - 0.1 \text{ min}^{-1}, P = 5-10 \text{ min}$

H_{β}

$v_2 = 0.4 - 0.5 \text{ min}^{-1} (P = 2-2.5 \text{ min})$
 $v_3 = 0.75 \text{ min}^{-1} (P = 1.3 \text{ min})$

Conclusions

- 1. The magnetic field distribution function $f(B)$ is probably the same for all OBA stars.*
- 2. It is still unclear why only $\sim 5-10\%$ of OBA stars are magnetic.*
- 3. Spectral observations with high time resolution show the presence of short-time variability, previously unknown for OBA stars.*
- 4. Line profile variations in spectra of HD 93521, ρ Leo and α 2CVn are likely related to high NRP modes.*
- 5. Fast line profile variations in the ρ Leo spectra with $v > 0.1 \text{ min}^{-1}$ and variable periods can be explained by the fast generation and decay of the NRP modes with $l \gg 1$.*